

Documentation of Ethnomedicinal Plants Used by Meitei Community in Manipur, India

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Introduction:

Manipur is one of the 7 sister states of the North-East India. Naturally, Manipur state is gifted with immense bio-resources and traditional treatment of ailments. Manipur's healthcare system has gone through several phases of development. In the early period, healthcare was primarily limited to traditional practices (Maiba and Maibi) and local remedies. However proper ethnobotanical study with scientific validation is less. This is the first attempt report that collects ethnomedicinal folk claims from different tribes of Central Valley districts of Manipur.

Methods:

An ethnobotanical survey was conducted to explore the traditional knowledge of medicinal plants being used by the Meitei community of Manipur, India. Semi-structured interviews were conducted among informants belonging to communities from the study area.

Results:

A total of 67 ethnomedicinal folk claims were collected. A total of 50 species belonging to 43 genera of 44 families were found to be utilized in remedy preparation. 15 claims were collected regarding Digestive ailments, 12 claims were reported for respiratory diseases, 10 claims for General and Unspecified diseases, 8 claims for Skin diseases, Endocrine/Metabolic, and Nutritionally related diseases, 7 claims for Urological diseases, 4 claims for Musculoskeletal diseases, 1 claim for Blood-related disease, Female Genital disease, and Neurological disease.

Conclusion:

Due to the rapid change in demographic patterns and urbanization of the area. The Socioeconomic condition of local people who are dependent on forest products has been compromised. The legacy of the ethno traditional knowledge of the community must be conserved in modern sustainable approaches. Both in-situ and ex-situ conservation techniques of medicinal plants should be encouraged for mass production.

Keywords: Manipur, Meitei Folk Healer, Ethnobotany, Traditional medicine.